

Title: International trade analysis of Benin with Nigeria and Africa

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Abstract:

Informal cross-border trade is important, widespread and sustainable in Africa. In this article, we will study the role of trade barriers in this air condition. We use our own research on unofficial cross-border transactions in Benin. It provides the first direct and comprehensive description of volume and product coverage for this type of transaction. Combine this data with official business records and take advantage of product and country differences to measure non-tariff and non-tariff barriers informally. Increasing tariffs on a particular product by 10% increases the likelihood that the product will be imported informally rather than officially from 12% to 14%. Non-tariff measures also increase informality. Our results also suggest that the cost of compliance, in addition to tariffs and regulations, helps to explain informally.

Keywords: Informal trade, Regional Integration, Trade facilitation, Evasion, Africa. JEL classification: O17, F15, H26

Introduction:

In this article, we study informal determinants of cross-border trade. This is a prevalent practice in many developing countries, especially Africa (Golub, 2015). Despite efforts to liberalize trade, occasional observations and case studies suggest that cross-border unrecorded commodity flows still represent a significant portion of the continent's international trade. .. The level of intra-African trade recorded in official data appears to be low by global standards, mainly due to the large proportion of transactions that cannot be recorded with this type of data¹. Here, we introduce the first quantitative study of informal cross-border trade based on comprehensive national data. Uses our own survey of cross-border transactions in all Benin borders unauthorized locations In West Africa, to document the size and composition of informal trade flows. Compare this data with customs data on legitimate trade in the same trade direction and duration to identify some of the informal determinants of trade. Associate tariff and non-tariff barriers with the likelihood that a particular product will be traded informally rather than formally. It also identifies product characteristics such as the ability to perish, which are actively associated with informal. The standard approach to informal trade is to consider it as a response to the excessive costs of legal trade. Multilateral agencies have called for non-tariff measures, tedious procedures, and intervention in exchange rates beyond tariffs, concluding that the African border remains thick (World Bank, 2012). However, the persistence of informal despite the progress of regional integration suggests that other potential factors may be at work. The state's ability to control borders and enforce taxes and regulations can play a role. Some people also see customary trade relations and long-used trade networks and routes as sources of informal permanence in situations where ethnic and trade relations are often inconsistent with national borders. .. The case of Benin is particularly relevant to the study of these questions. A small and

poor French-speaking country, he is a founding member of UEMO A2, a currency and customs union in eight West African countries.

It shares borders with three members, UEMOA, Togo, Burkina Faso and Niger, mainly agricultural countries like Benin (see Figure 1). WAEMU countries have gradually dismantled internal charges, simplified the structure and implemented a common external charge (CET) with a maximum rate of 20%. Benin's fourth and final frontier is Nigeria, the continent's largest economy. Nigeria and Benin also share a broader regional agreement than UEMOA, ECOWAS3 membership, but trade liberalization has not progressed so far. In 2011, ECOWAS did not liberalize domestic trade, except for certain raw products. In addition to tariff peaks, Nigeria has a number of non-tariff barriers and protectionist policies with import bans. The currency is non-convertible and chronically overvalued (IMF, 2017). Thus, the Benin border provides us with case studies of trade liberalization at various stages and gives us the opportunity to examine their impact on trade informatics.

Gathering data on informal activities is inherently difficult. Empirical exercises address concerns about data reliability and representativeness. Despite these inherent difficulties, the survey provides a very rich vision of informal trade at the border of Benin. The ECENE Survey (Unregistered Foreign Trade Survey) was conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics of Benin (INSAE) in 2011. 171 border crossings have been identified and investigated. A total of 8,883 traders were surveyed and 10,415 unique product flows were recorded. All of these intersections are on land boundaries and are separate from the official boundaries. This shows the definition of informal trading in this document. This represents all cross-border transactions that take place outside the official intersection. Our results shed new light on some aspects of the question. First, we confirm the quantitative importance of informal trade in the region. It is often several times higher than formal value trade. For trade with Nigeria, the informal / official ratio is about 7.2 for imports, It is estimated to be 5.1 for exports. As a result, the situation of regional trade integration changes dramatically when informal trade is taken into account. Trade between Benin and Nigeria is not important in official trade data.

Data and descriptive statistics

The analysis in this article relies primarily on two data sources, recording informal and official cross-border trade flows between Benin and its immediate neighbors. The first source is ECENE (non-formal), a survey conducted by INSAE's Benin National Accounts in 2011 with the aim of more accurately estimating the size and composition of informal trade and reporting on this factor. Registered trade survey). In the national accounts. The institute first identified 171 illegal border crossings that were actively used by informal traders, scattered along the Benin border. Figure 2 shows the range of survey points¹⁰. These intersections were investigated in September 2011 by a team of 350 investigators, 30 managers and 12 supervisors for 10 days during the day. A four-page questionnaire was given to informal traders, along with questions about the nature, quantity and value of smuggled goods, the origin and destination of shipments, and the mode of transport. The product is coded with a high level of detail (Harmonized Product Description and Classification Coding System, HS-10 10-digit code). A total of 8,883 questionnaires were completed and 10,415 unique product flows were recorded and retained after laboratory data

cleaning (compared to the 10,749 flows of primary data) (INSAE, 2011). Trade flows are divided into exports, imports, re-exports and transportation. These last two categories correspond to the flow of goods occurring in a third country (usually Asia or Europe) and before reaching one of the countries across one of Benin's borders (probably legal). Enter Benin. In the context of this article, we focus on regional trade. Therefore, it ignores so-called warehousing trade (re-exports and transport flows), which are likely to have different determinants and require separate analysis¹¹. Therefore, the results of imports and exports from Benin are shown directly. neighbor.

Nigeria's Trade Policies Create Distortions That Incentivize Smuggling

Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil and many dysfunctional economic policies have created an environment that allows ICBT to thrive between Nigeria and its neighbors, primarily Benin and Togo. A big gap between the official rate and the naira black market rate. Nigerian subsidized fuel prices. Import Barriers (Table 1); Weak Trade Facilitation (Table 2); Benin's poor business environment has led local traders to look to informal cross-border trade.

	2001	2007	2015	2020	
1995					
Beer	Banned	100	Banned	Banned	Banned
Cloth and apparel	Banned	55	Banned	Banned	45/ Forex ban**
Poultry meat	Banned	75	Banned	Banned	Banned
Rice	100	75	50	100	70***
Sugar	10	40	50	60	70
Cigarettes	90	80	50	50	95
Used cars*	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned / 70
Vegetable oil	Banned	40	Banned	Banned	Banned

Source: Local government body

* The maximum age of banned vehicles will change over time, from 8 years in 1995, 5 years in 2001, 8 years in 2007, and 17 years in 2020. Also, since 2016, imports have been banned by borders. Use the official Forex market. *** Rice imports have been banned across national borders since 2013.

Magnitude Of Entrepôt Trade Between Benin And Nigeria

Contraband is of course difficult to measure, but it can be indirectly estimated from the size of the official per capita import of Benin compared to Nigeria and other countries. Import of certain highly protected products in Nigeria, such as cars, clothing, rice and poultry, into Benin per capita

Effects On National Income, Employment, And Tax Revenues

As in other countries, the effects of ICBT on Benin are mixed. For example, ICBT produces about 20% of Benin's GDP. Gasoline smuggling employs about 40,000 people, about the same size as Benin's public sector, and it is estimated that the direct and indirect jobs of used car smuggling are about 15,000 and 100,000, respectively. I will. On the other hand, the long-term impact on economic growth and diversification can be negative. ICBT attracts entrepreneurial talent to informal, illegal, or quasi-legal activities rather than the potentially more productive sector. Moreover, the involvement of high-ranking government officials in informal activities at all levels makes reform much more difficult.

Conclusion:

Informal cross-border trade is widespread and sustainable in many developing regions, especially in Africa. This article explores the relationship between trade barriers and informal relations using an extensive survey of informal trade at the Benin border conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics in September 2011. First, data for all flows that estimate the size of informal flows. We show that accounting for informal trade can significantly change the image of regional trade and confirm that West Africa's regional trade integration is significantly undervalued in official trade data. Second, it measures informal positive semi-elasticity with respect to tariffs. Increasing tariffs on a particular product by 10% increases the likelihood that the product will be imported informally rather than officially from 12% to 14%. In addition, non-tariff measures have also increased informality, The ad valorem tax for SPS measures is equivalent to about 23-30%. Local raw products are more likely to be traded informally, even though tariffs on this transaction have been completely eliminated. The ability to perish is also informally related, suggesting that time as a trade barrier partially influences informal choices. Differentiated products are much less likely to be traded through informal routes. The tariff effect is large, but lower than the equivalent estimate of tax evasion, which has been the subject of the most quantitative study of tax evasion in international trade to date. This shows that the economics of trading on unauthorized routes, which is the subject of this article, is different from the economics of other forms of fraud. As a result, the impact on policy is also different. Tariff cuts may not increase revenue. To reduce informalities, it may be necessary to address other informal drivers beyond tariffs and regulations.

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